

DETERMINANTS OF CONTRACEPTIVE USE AMONG MARRIED WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN: AN ANALYTICAL CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Contraceptive usage is a significant element of reproductive health. Despite putting so many efforts to control population growth and family planning in developing countries, the use of contraceptive remains suboptimal particularly in low- and middle-income families. Considering the demographic factors affecting contraceptive usage to initiate targeted interventions and bring the positive outcome in family planning services.

Objective: To assess the role of socioeconomic status on the contraceptive's usage amongst married women in Karachi, Pakistan.

Method: An analytical cross-sectional study conducted among 400 married women under reproductive age group (15-49 years old) belong to low- and middle-income households in two different areas of Karachi Pakistan. Participants were recruited via non-probability convenient sampling. Structured questionnaire tool was employed for data collection. For analysis, SPSS version 22 was used. The descriptive data was calculated through frequency and percentages whereas the inferential data was retrieved by using chi-square test.

Results: The study results showed that around 49% of the participants were using family planning methods. The socio-demographic characteristics such as area of residence, number of children, employment status, monthly income, awareness and current usage of family planning methods were significantly associated with the family planning utilization. The level of education and age did not have impact of family planning utilization.

Conclusion: In conclusion, our study sheds light on geographic location, economic conditions, family dynamics, employment status, and awareness levels are key determinants of family planning utilization. These findings underscore the importance of targeted interventions that address these factors to enhance the uptake of family planning methods. Conversely, factors like education level, age, and decisions on future pregnancies do not significantly influence FP utilization, suggesting that these areas might require different approaches or are less critical in the context studied.

INTRODUCTION

A high rate of population growth in Pakistan and its adverse impact on successful implementation of sustainable development strategies have long been recognized. On the other hand, a remarkable decline in global fertility rates in general and in developing countries in particular has been observed over the last twenty years, due to an increase in the use of contraceptives. According to Demographic and Health survey the low use of contraceptives and associated hindrances has been explained by different studies examining various dimensions Health concerns, side effects, failure of the methods and some demographic issues, among which education, age, and number of daughters, have a great influence on the using contraceptive measures [1]. To achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) contraception play a significant role, the use of contraceptives is an important factor to consider if one wants to manage the population explosion It aims to eradicate poverty, hunger, lowering infant and maternal mortality, fostering good health, gender equality, and also aids women's empowerment. For increase population, there may be consequences of facing food crisis, which could upset the balance of power and cause unrest. Therefore, it is important to look into the prevalence of contraceptive use, which, if widely used, could be beneficial from a family planning standpoint [2].

Family planning is the process of controlling the quantity, timing, and spacing of births by using birth control methods such as modern contraceptives. The Contraceptive Prevalence rate is predicated on the basis of contemporary (modern) and conventional (traditional) methods usage. Mostly sterilization of both partners of couple, intrauterine devices (IUDs), pills, injections, implants, and condoms are used in modern contraceptives. Other less used modern contraceptives include diaphragm and lactation amenorrhea, foam or spermicidal, and fertility awareness methods. Whereas, periodic abstinence, withdrawal, and other folkloric techniques are called as traditional methods (TM). The percentage of people using modern methods—far exceeds that of traditional methods [3]. For people to have the freedom to decide for them what is best for their reproductive health and well-being, family planning is necessary. Together with lowering the rate of

unwanted births, high-risk pregnancies, and maternal and newborn deaths, it also enhances children's nutrition and health, increases educational attainment, and improves economic results, especially for women and girls [4]. In low- and lower-middle-income regions primarily encompass the countries where modern contraceptive methods meet less than half of the demand for family planning. Southern Asia, for instance, reports the highest number of women with an unmet need, reaching 87 million [5]. Services related to family planning significantly affect the morbidity and mortality of mothers. Maternal mortality and disability from pregnancy and childbirth problems are greatly reduced as the prevalence of contraceptives rises and the unmet need for family planning decline. Despite this, millions of women worldwide endure the unacceptable consequences of undesired and/or mistimed births every year [6].

Gender inequality and women's inferior status are ingrained in cultural norms in historically patriarchal nations such as Pakistan, preventing women from both receiving healthcare facilities and participating in health-related decision-making. The lack of autonomy and earning options for women exacerbates this discrepancy. Furthermore, FP knowledge and practice are highly predicted by women's employment status, education level, and concerns about fertility. As the awareness of family planning methods among women increases, the tendency towards family planning increases. Understanding FP is a crucial precondition for raising CPR. Only 25% of married women of reproductive age (MWRA) in Pakistan use contemporary contraceptives, despite the fact that all men (98.6%) and women (98.1%) are aware of these techniques. This highlights a gap between knowledge and practice. The term "know-do gap" refers to the discrepancy between behavior and knowledge regarding contraception [7]. Pakistan, classified as a lower-middle-income nation, according to the 2023 census has a population of 241.5 million, ranking as the fifth most populous country globally [8]. The lack of Government support, proper planning, decision-making subject to reproductive health, individual false beliefs about the application and adverse effects of contraceptive techniques [9]. On the supply side, it

has been noted that infrequent availability of contraceptive methods, unsatisfactory attitude and skill of healthcare professionals, and restricted availability and outreach of family planning services are important barriers to uptake [10].

An analytical study conducted in Pakistan consisting of sample size 40,259 married women in reproductive age. The results showed only 30 percent of women were using contraception. Of these, 26% women used conventional methods and majority (74%) used contemporary methods. Condom use was the most popular method of contraception (30.5%). Age of women, residential area, education level, employment status, wealth index, and exposure to family planning messages were revealed to be significant predictors of contraceptive usage by multivariate analysis [11]. This is still lower than the neighboring countries, i.e. Bangladesh and India. The prevalence rate in Bangladesh and in India is 62% and 52.2% respectively [12]. However, according to the most recent Annual Contraceptive Performance (ACP) Report for 2019-20 by the Government of Pakistan showed, overall contraceptive use has declined by 8.3% compared to the previous year [13]. Underutilization of FP methods is thought to be more common among women in the younger age group, who are illiterate, and who have less experience with FP services [14]. It is considered that with the increase in women's education level her decision-making power increases which also has a great impact on opting family planning methods. Research indicated that the use of family planning techniques were positively correlated with men's decision-making authority [15]. Demand for or consumption of any service is heavily influenced by wealth or economic standing of families. Studies revealed a favorable correlation between better socio-economic condition and the use of family planning services. Another factor such as people's decision-making is also influenced by their religion. Family planning is regarded as against Islam in Pakistan, where the majority of the population is Muslim, as a result of incorrect interpretations of the religion's teachings or ignorance of them, which poses a significant barrier to its use. In Pakistan, men always predominate, and their decisions are highly valued in any situation. In choosing the size of the family or the number of children, the husband's

approval is crucial, just like it is in all other decisions. Higher utilization of family planning services is correlated with husband's approval [16]. One of the main factors influencing the use of family planning services has been identified as the number of living children. Compared to families with a smaller family size, those with a higher number of live children are more likely to use family planning techniques. Tendency of own preferred method also plays a major role in choosing family planning services. Previous reports have highlighted that the couples who desire more number of children are less intending to use any family planning method [17]. Different influencing factors such as fear of side effects, inadequate family support, knowledge, availability and accessibility of FP services has been recognized in literature that are associated with underutilization of family planning methods and techniques [18]. The objective of this study is to assess the role of socioeconomic status on the contraceptive's usage amongst married women in Karachi, Pakistan.

METHODS:

Analytical cross-sectional study design was conducted, which involved data collection at specific time which represented a sample of married women in reproductive age group. The study was conducted in the settings of two maternity homes located in Garden East and Sultanabad Karachi, Pakistan. These areas constitute of diverse sample with different levels of education, distinct socio-economic backgrounds, and accessibility of healthcare. The study was conducted in the duration of eight months, started after receiving ethical approval from the Ethical Review Committee (ERC) in October 2023. The study was finalized in the month of May 2024. The sample size calculation was done by using OpenEpi software, with a predicted value of contraception usage 50% and 95% of confidence interval, whereas the confidence limit was 5% and design effect of 1 according to the survey of Demographic Health. The minimum sample size calculated was 382. But finally, 400 participants were recruited for missing data and to reduce the response bias. The sample was selected on the basis systematic random selection.

Inclusion criteria are participants included women having marital status of legally married with ages between 15 to 49 years. This criterion focused on the understanding contraceptive decision-making only in marital relationships. Participants must be residing in the selected communities of Karachi (Garden East, and Sultanabad Community) and must be native residents. Exclusive criteria are women who refused to give their willingness in participation or signing their informed consent were excluded from the study. Also, the women who were above the ages of 18 to 49 years were not included and non-pregnant. A structured questionnaire was used which specifically developed to assess on different elements relevant to the objectives of the study. It included different contraceptive methods used, socio-demographic characteristics, and other factors which were putting impact on contraceptive practices among married couples. The data collection permission were taken from Medical Superintendent of Sindh Government Hospital Karachi (Reference no: SGHL/6177, Dated: 07-05-24) and from Vice-chairman of union council-1 Pakistan quarter Jinnah

town district east Karachi (Reference no: 0086/23, Dated: 17-11-23). Before filling the questionnaire, enumerators obtained informed consent from each participants. Initial descriptive statistics employed to characterize the study population, providing insights into the distribution of variables such as couple education levels and contraceptive practices. Inferential statistical method, including chi-square was used to assess the relationship between women’s characteristics and contraceptive use. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 22.0) was used to perform data analysis, ensuring accuracy and robustness in the statistical procedures.

RESULTS:

Amongst the total of 400 Women’s included in the study, the mean age was 29.99±4.89 years while their husbands mean age was 34.885±5.47 years. The mean number of children was reported to be 2.88±1.38. Mean age of women at marriage was 21.82±2.70 years. The mean number of people living in each house was 5.35±1.37 [Table IA].

Table IA: Baseline information regarding Women (n=400)

Variable	Mean ± SD
Age (years)	29.99 ± 4.89
Husband’s age (years)	34.885 ± 5.47
Number of children	2.88 ± 1.38
Age at marriage (years)	21.82 ± 2.70
How many people are there in this house?	5.35 ± 1.37

The finding of the study suggested that majority of the families 49.5% had 1 or 2 children. 35%

families had 3 or 4 children, and 15.5% had 5 or more children. (Table IB)

Table- IB :Number of children (n=400)

Range	Frequency	Percentage
None	0	0
1-2	198	49.5
3-4	140	35
5 or more	62	15.5

In terms of education status of participants, 2.1 % were illiterate, 16.5 % had completed matriculation, 126.8 % had completed intermediate, 38.8 % had

completed Bachelors and 16.1 % had completed masters or equivalent degrees [Table II].

Table II: Education status of participants included in the study (n=400)

Variable	n	%	
Level of education	Masters or Equivalent	64	16.1
	Bachelor	155	38.8

	Intermediate	107	26.8
	Matriculation	66	16.5
	NIL	8	2.1

With regards to the employment status of participants included in the study, 42.8 % are currently employed, 15.3 % are health care

professionals, 21 % are teacher, 8.75 % are office workers, 13 % are unemployed [Table III].

Table III: Employment status of participants included in the study (n=400)

Variable		n	%
If currently working?	Yes	171	42.8
	No	229	57.3
	House Wife	166	41.6
	Health Care Professional	61	15.3
	Teaching	84	21
	Office worker	35	8.7
	Unemployed	52	13.0

As shown in table IV over two thirds 68.5% of respondents were born in a city while 31.5 % were born in rural areas. 97 % could visit the doctor or local health care center alone. Regarding family planning 71.3 % reported it meant spacing delay between children, 18.1 % consider it means to limit family size, and 10.5 % are of the opinion that when

after using family planning method a woman cannot be bear any children. When asked whether family planning is against Islamic teachings, 43.8 % replied yes, 30.3 % said no while 126 % did not know whether family planning is against Islamic teachings or not. About 49.3 % of women or their husband had at least once used family planning [Table IV].

Table IV: Information regarding contraception among participants (n=400)

Variable		n	%
Place of Birth	A rural Area	126	31.5
	City	274	68.5
Visit to doctor/local health center alone	Yes	388	97.0
	No	12	3.0
Opinion about family planning	Spacing delay	285	71.3
	Limiting family size	72	18.1
	No more children can be born after using FP	42	10.5
Opinion about is family planning against Islamic teachings?	Yes	175	43.8
	No	121	30.3
	Don't Know	104	26.0
Currently using any family planning method	Yes	197	49.3
	No	203	50.8

Of the respondents, 4.3 % had used IUD, 21.8 % had used condoms, 13.3 % practiced the withdrawal method, 2.3 % used oral tablets, 0.5 % practiced abstinence, 5.8 % used oral pills, and 1.3 % used

injections. Currently, 49.3 % of the respondents or their husbands use some form of family planning method, while 50.8 % did not [Table V].

Table V: Information about methods used for contraceptive use (n=400)

Variable		n	%
Family planning methods used in the	IUD	17	4.3

past	Condom	87	21.8
	Withdrawal	53	13.3
	Abstinence	2	0.5
	Oral Pill.	32	8.1
	Injections	5	1.3
Currently using any family planning method?	Yes	197	49.3
	No	203	50.8

About whose idea it was to use a method of family planning, 22.3% stated that it was the husband, while 17.5 % said it was their own idea. When asked about the main reasons for never using a method to delay or prevent pregnancy, 30.0 % indicated they wanted children, 17.4 % cited side effects,

7.5% mentioned difficulty in obtaining methods, 0.5 % attributed it to breastfeeding, 0.3 % due to religious reasons. In general, 45.8% of respondents approved of couples using family planning methods to delay or avoid pregnancy, 26.8 % disapproved while 27.5 % are unsure about it [Table VI].

Table VI: Reasons for never using contraceptive methods for family planning (n=400)

Variable		n	%
Who's Preference of using family planning (husband or wife)?	Husband	89	22.3
	Own	70	17.5
Reasons for never using family planning method	Want children	120	30.0
	Side Effects	69	17.4
	Hard to obtain methods	30	7.5
	Breastfeeding	2	0.5
	Religious reason	1	0.3
Acceptance of family planning method	Yes	183	45.8
	No	107	26.8
	Don't Know	110	27.5

Regarding the approval of family planning methods among friends and neighbors, 59.8 % of respondents stated that most of their friends and neighbors approve of it, while 13.5 % said they do not approve, and 26.8 % are unsure. When asked about the appropriate time after marriage to consult a caregiver if a couple is unable to have children, 42.5 %

suggested after one year, 8.0 % suggested after two years, 8.8 % suggested after three years, and 24.8 % believed it should be immediate. In terms of opinions on who should be investigated for infertility, 4.0 % indicated only the husband, 9.0 % indicated only the wife, 75.8 % believed both should be investigated, and 11.0 % did not know [Table VII].

Table VII: Approval about contraceptive methods among participants (n=400)

Variable		n	%
Acceptance of family planning methods among friends or neighbors	Yes	239	59.8
	No	54	13.5
	Don't Know	107	26.8
Appropriate time to consult a caregiver for children after marriage?	After 1 year	170	42.5
	After 2 year	32	8.0
	After 3 year	35	8.8
	Immediate	99	24.8
Opinion on who should be investigated for infertility	Only husband	16	4.0
	Only wife	36	9.0
	Both of them	303	75.8

	Don't know	44	11.0
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When asked if they sought any treatment to have children at any time after marriage, 13.5 %sought treatment from a doctor, while 85.5 %did not seek any treatment. Of those who sought treatment with a doctor, 13.0 %reported a positive outcome.

Additionally, none of the respondents reported that their husband sought treatment, with 100.0 % indicating that their husband did not seek any treatment to have children after marriage [Table VIII]

Table VIII: Treatment sought by participants included in the study (n=400)

Variable		n	%
"Ever sought treatment to have children after marriage?"	Yes, doctor	54	13.5
	No One	342	85.5
	Yes, the homeopath or Hakeem	2	0.6
outcome after treatment for family planning	Positive	52	13.0
	Not Positive	3	0.8
Husband ever sought treatment to have children after marriage?	Yes	0	0.0
	No	400	100.0

Table IX shows the chi square analysis of independent variables with Family planning utilization of husband and wife. It shows that there is a highly significant association between:

1. Area of Residence: There is a highly significant association between FP utilization and the area of residence ($\chi^2 = 119.766, p = .000$). This suggests that where a person lives significantly influences their use of FP methods, potentially due to differences in access to healthcare services, cultural norms, or socioeconomic conditions.
2. Number of Children: The analysis reveals a significant association between FP utilization and the number of children ($\chi^2 = 28.599, p = .000$). Families with more children are more likely to use FP methods, possibly to manage family size and ensure better resource allocation.
3. Relationship with Spouse: The quality of the relationship with one's spouse ($\chi^2 = 17.532, p = .001$) and who chose the spouse ($\chi^2 = 30.093, p = .000$) are significant predictors of FP utilization. These factors may reflect the level of communication and agreement between partners on reproductive health decisions.
4. Employment Status: Employment status ($\chi^2 = 52.104, p = .000$) significantly affects FP utilization. Employed individuals may have better access to information and services related to FP and a greater ability to afford these services.
5. Monthly Income: Monthly income ($\chi^2 = 85.514, p = .000$) is a strong determinant of FP utilization.

Higher income levels correlate with higher FP use, likely due to better access to healthcare and greater financial resources to support family planning choices.

6. Awareness and Current Usage of FP Methods: Awareness of FP methods ($\chi^2 = 253.409, p = .000$) and current usage of FP ($\chi^2 = 303.828, p = .000$) are highly associated with FP utilization. Awareness campaigns and education on FP methods can significantly impact their usage rates.
7. Last Utilized FP Method: The last utilized FP method ($\chi^2 = 66.680, p = .000$) is significantly associated with FP utilization, indicating that previous experiences with FP methods can influence continued use.
8. Approval of Family Planning: Approval of family planning ($\chi^2 = 53.031, p = .000$) is significantly associated with its utilization. Social and familial approval can play a crucial role in the decision to use FP methods.
9. Homeownership: Homeownership ($\chi^2 = 41.336, p = .000$) is significantly associated with FP utilization, suggesting that more stable and permanent living conditions might encourage family planning. However, factors including Non-Significant Associations that is:
 1. Age of Participants: The age of participants ($\chi^2 = 36.548, p = .064$) does not significantly influence FP utilization.
 2. Age When Starting to Live with a Spouse: The age when participants started living with their spouse

($\chi^2 = 16.211, p = .238$) is not significantly associated with FP utilization.

3. Level of Education: The level of education ($\chi^2 = 4.2725, p = .370$) does not show a significant impact on FP utilization.

4. Decision on Future Pregnancies: Decisions regarding future pregnancies ($\chi^2 = .656, p = .720$) are not significantly associated with FP utilization.

Table IX: Chi square analysis of independent variables with Family planning utilization

Variable	Chi-square value	p-value
Current use of Contraceptive* Areas of Residence (Lower and Middle)	119.766	.000
Current use of Contraceptive* Age of wife?	36.548	.064
Current use of Contraceptive* Age of husband?	52.869	.006
Current use of Contraceptive * Number of children	28.599	.000
Current use of Contraceptive *Any blood relationship between husband and wife?	17.532	.001
Current use of Contraceptive? * Age at the time of marriage	16.211	.238
Current use of Contraceptive* level of education	4.2725	.370
Current use of Contraceptive* Current employment status.	52.104	.000
Current use of Contraceptive* Estimated monthly income	85.514	.000
Current use of Contraceptive*Place of birth (Rural area or City)	37.894	.000
Current use of Contraceptive* Awareness of family planning Method?	253.409	.000
Current use of Contraceptive* Idea of using the family planning method (husband or wife)?	223.853	.000
Current use of Contraceptive* House ownership	41.336	.000

DISCUSSION:

This study's primary goal was to determine the socioeconomic and demographic elements that effect women in reproductive-age to use various contraceptive methods. The study results showed that around 49%of the participants were using family planning methods. However, studies from other areas of Pakistan reported overall contraceptive prevalence rate is 34%, which is still less than Bangladesh [19]. Although lot of efforts are taken by Pakistan government but still the low prevalence rate of contraceptive use among married women in reproductive age differs by demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of participants which include lack of motivation, familial restrictions, social constraints, communication gap among couple, lack of awareness and financial issues to access family planning services. The findings of present study

revealed that the most common method of contraception was condoms. Similar findings were also reported in the research study conducted in Pakistan reported that 30% of respondents considered the use of condoms as a method of contraception [20].

Our study results conclude that significant differences exist in the likelihood of contraceptive use based on various socio-economic, educational, and demographic factors. Middle-income individuals are much more likely to use contraceptives compared to those with low income, highlighting the strong influence of socio-economic status. This finding indicates that higher income levels are associated with increased odds of contraceptive use. Similar results were found in the multilevel analysis which showed that women with middle and higher economic status were more likely to utilize

contraceptives than poor women [21]. Employment status was a very strong predictor, as the odds of contraceptive use were higher in employed than non-employed individuals. These results suggest that employment might influence contraceptive use, possibly through mechanisms having to do with money (e.g., financial stress), social capital (disruption of networks) or psychological burden.

Demographically, contraceptive use seems to be low irrespective of age. This is offset by the strong association between higher contraceptive use and additional children; suggesting that family size has a significant outcome on the chance of using contraceptives. On the other hand, larger family size appears to reduce likelihood of use, reflecting a beneficial influence of co-residence with more relatives as connected to shared responsibilities or networks of aid within the household. The findings of current study reported that awareness of family planning methods was significantly associated with family planning utilization. Awareness campaigns and education on FP methods can significantly impact their usage rates. The study conducted in country reported that increase family planning utilization were found in women who had knowledge about contraceptives [22].

Moreover this study showed that highly significant association found between family planning utilization and the area of residence. Similarly the research study reported that the type of place of residence such as urban and rural has a significant impact on family planning utilization [23]. The current study revealed that the level of education does not show a significant impact on family planning utilization. In contrast the research study reported that level of Education plays a crucial role, with higher educational attainment correlating with increased likelihood of contraceptive use [24]. Furthermore the result of this study reported that the age of participants does not significantly influence family planning utilization. The opposite results found in the study conducted at showed that the maternal age was significantly associated with the family planning [25].

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, our study sheds light on Socio-economic conditions, family dynamics, employment

status, and awareness levels which are key determinants of family planning utilization. Study finding highlighted that socio demographic variables such as occupation, socioeconomic status, cultural influence, and previous experiences affect family planning practices significantly among study population. Moreover, participants having awareness about family planning methods, family acceptance about Family planning usage are also strong determinants of Family planning practice. However, participant age, level of education do not affect family planning practices among couples. Therefore, health care professionals in primary health setup should take step forward in spreading quality information regarding family planning practices to newly married couples, and stakeholders who are decision makers in the family. Further researches can be conducted in other communities and localities to make study findings more generalizable. Interventions such as workshops, seminars, and word of mouth through social media can motivate and educate people to use good family planning practice in order to improve maternal and child health.

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